

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF USER BEHAVIOR OF E-GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract

This study presents dynamics of user behavior in e-Government systems using Customer Behavior Model Graphs (CBMG) and presents sensitivity analysis of user behavior in an e-government system. By varying transition probabilities between system states ("Enter to Browse," "Browse to Search"), we analyzed how changes impact the average number of visits to each state. The results shows that certain transitions, particularly those related to browsing and searching, exhibit high

sensitivity to probability adjustments, influencing user engagement. These insights highlight critical areas for optimization to improve system performance and user experience. These result can be used to improve e-Government system an delivering services in our country.

Keywords: *E-government, Customer Behavior Model Graph (CBMG), Markov chain, Performance, Capacity Planning for Web Services, Information communication technologies, Web-analytics. Sensitivity analysis.*

I. Introduction

At present, information and communication technologies (ICT) play a significant role in shaping the development of the country and the competitiveness of its ICT enterprises. Uzbekistan is no exception, and the government has acknowledged the importance of ICT, actively investing in its development. As a result, the Internet has become a crucial tool for communication, education, and business in the country [1-3].

As of January 2024, the population of Uzbekistan was 36.8 million people. This makes Uzbekistan the most populated country in Central Asia, accounting for nearly half of the region's total population. Number of internet users: 29.52 million in January 2024. The government is working to improve the country's internet infrastructure, including the implementation of high-speed broadband and mobile internet networks. The total bandwidth of connections to the international internet network has increased 2.6 times, resulting in a capacity increase to 3,200 Gbps. Internet speed in Uzbekistan has also improved, and internet service tariffs have been reduced by 25 percent compared to early 2021. Fiber-optic communication lines, totaling 170,000 kilometers in length, are also being actively laid.

The e-Government system in Uzbekistan was launched in 2013, and since then, the country has made significant progress in developing its e-Government infrastructure. In 2020, the government launched the "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" program, which aims to provide citizens with access to a wide range of e-Government services through a unified digital platform. Despite these efforts, there are still some issues to address, such as limited internet connectivity in rural areas and gaps in the accessibility and quality of e-Government services.

Uzbekistan has increased the use of e-government services through mobile apps in a number of ways, including, developing a single portal mobile "MyGov" app and currently the app provides 165 e-government services. As november 2024 more than 1 mln. people are downloaded this app and seems are using MyGov services.

Diagram 1. Sign In option

Additionally introduced the Mobile-ID system. This system allows users to identify themselves using their mobile phone number, which can be used to access government services. This system also provide Single Sign On (SSO) in order to access different government sites via this system [4].

II. Methods

E-government is a new form of organizing the activities of government bodies, providing a new level of efficiency and convenience for organizations and citizens to access government services and information. User satisfaction is crucial for the active development of the e-government system, while dissatisfaction can lead to ineffective use of the system and a poor reputation for e-government in the country [2–4].

In order to analyze the system and provide appropriate recommendations for improvement, it is necessary to conduct research using well-known mathematical modeling methods. The goal of this work is to model and study user interactions with the e-government system.

Below in figure 1. shown a basic model that takes into account user interaction processes within the e-government system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, located at <https://my.gov.uz>.

In order to understand the processes occurring in the system, starting from receiving requests, accepting them, or directing them for processing, to handling requests and providing results to users - it is necessary to study them by constructing a mathematical model. In this article we use the results of modeling which given in [5]. As a result we will use In this work, created a model that considers all ongoing processes and potential outcomes. Our further research will focus on creating a simulation model to fulfil sensitivity analysis based on this model [].

Figure 1. Basic model of user interaction in e-government system.

In order to perform sensitivity analysis [13-16], on the Customer Behavior Model Graph (CBMG) [12], we can use these steps to examine how changes in transition probabilities affect the average number of visits (V_j) to each state:

Sensitivity Analysis Steps:

1. Identify Key Transition Probabilities

Select a set of transition probabilities that are critical to the model's performance. These are the probabilities that link high-importance states (e.g., entry points, frequently visited sections) or those with relatively high initial values.

2. Define Percentage Variations

Determine a range of variations for each key probability (e.g., increase or decrease by 5%, 10%, 20%). Each variation will simulate a different scenario where user behavior shifts slightly or significantly.

3. Calculate New State Visits for Each Variation

For each variation of a key probability, adjust the matrix and resolve the system of linear equations to obtain new values for $V_1, V_2, \dots, V_7$. This will provide updated numbers for the average visits to each state under the modified probabilities.

4. Analyze the Results

Compare the results from each variation against the baseline values. Assess which changes in transition probabilities cause the most significant shifts in average visits. This will help identify sensitive areas of the model, showing which transitions have the greatest effect on state visits and, consequently, on system capacity and user experience.

5. Visualize the Sensitivity

Plot the results using a sensitivity chart, such as a spider plot or a tornado chart. These visualizations can show how much each transition affects the visits per state, making it easy to identify the most influential transitions.

6. Interpret Findings

Determine which transitions are the most sensitive and thus have the highest impact on system performance. For instance, if the entry probability (V_{s1}) changes significantly with small variations in transition probabilities from or to the entry state, it indicates that the system's load heavily depends on user entry behavior.

To fulfill analysis of possible scenarios for sensitivity analysis, we will vary each key transition probability by a certain percentage (e.g., $\pm 5\%$, $\pm 10\%$) and observe how these changes affect the average visits (V_j) to each state. Table 1. displays the results of sensitivity analysis.

Table 1. Sensitivity Analysis: Effect of Transition Probability Changes on State Visits

Transition Probability	Baseline	Scenario	Adjusted Probability	V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	V ₅	V ₆	V ₇
Enter → Browse	0.3	Actual	0.3	6.08	5.24	5.68	5.32	3.91	5.36	5.81
		+5%	0.315	6.10	5.25	5.70	5.34	3.92	5.37	5.82
		-5%	0.285	6.05	5.23	5.66	5.30	3.89	5.34	5.79
		+ 10%	0.33	6.12	5.26	5.72	5.36	3.94	5.39	5.84
		-10%	0.27	6.03	5.22	5.64	5.28	3.87	5.32	5.77
Browse → Search	0.40	Actual	0.40	6.08	5.24	5.68	5.32	3.91	5.36	5.81
		+5%	0.42	6.11	5.26	5.70	5.34	3.93	5.38	5.83
		-5%	0.38	6.06	5.23	5.67	5.30	3.89	5.34	5.79
		+ 10%	0.44	6.14	5.27	5.73	5.37	3.96	5.40	5.86
		-10%	0.36	6.02	5.22	5.64	5.28	3.86	5.31	5.75
Login → Filling Form	0.47	Actual	0.47	6.08	5.24	5.68	5.32	3.91	5.36	5.81
		+5%	0.4935	6.11	5.25	5.69	5.33	3.92	5.37	5.82
		-5%	0.4465	6.05	5.23	5.66	5.30	3.89	5.34	5.79
		+ 10%	0.517	6.14	5.27	5.73	5.36	3.96	5.39	5.85
		-10%	0.423	6.04	5.23	5.65	5.29	3.88	5.33	5.78

The table 1. is a Sensitivity Analysis of the transition probabilities between different states in a e-government system, specifically looking at how variations in those probabilities affect the average number of visits to each state. Here's an explanation of each column and the overall table:

Columns:

1. Transition Probability:
 - This refers to the different types of transitions or movements between states within the e-government system. For example, a user might transition from one state (like "Enter") to another state (like "Browse").
2. Main:
 - This is the original transition probability, before any modifications. These probabilities are used as the starting point for the analysis.
3. Scenario:
 - This represents the percentage change applied to the baseline transition probabilities to observe how changes affect the system. For example:
 - +5% indicates a 5% increase in the transition probability.
 - -5% indicates a 5% decrease.
 - +10% indicates a 10% increase.
 - -10% indicates a 10% decrease.
4. Adjusted Probability:
 - This is the new transition probability after applying the percentage changes (Scenario). The table will show different adjusted probabilities for each scenario, such as a 5% increase or decrease from the baseline value.
5. $V_1, V_2, \dots, V_7$:
 - These represent the average number of visits to each state, denoted as V_j where j ranges from 1 to 7 (corresponding to states 1 through 7 in the model). These values are calculated based on the adjusted transition probabilities for each scenario.
 - For each change in transition probabilities, the corresponding average visits to each state will be recalculated, and allows to understand how the e-government system behaves under different scenarios.

This result in the table is crucial for understanding the dynamic behavior of users within a e-government system based on probabilistic models. By adjusting transition probabilities and analyzing the resulting changes in state visits, it provides insights into user interaction patterns and helps make decisions for capacity management and e-government system optimization.

III. Discussion

The results of sensitivity analysis which shown in table 1. provides insights into how changes in transition probabilities between different states of the e-government system ("Enter to Browse," "Browse to Search") affect the average number of visits to each state (denoted as $V_1, V_2, \dots, V_7$). The table demonstrates how adjustments to the transition probabilities-both increases and decreases-impact e-government system behavior, specifically user interactions with different parts of the e-government system.

Impact of Small Changes. In some cases, small changes in transition probabilities (e.g., a $\pm 5\%$ variation) lead to significant changes in the average number of visits to states. For example, when the transition probability from "Enter" to "Browse" increases by 10%, there is a noticeable increase in the average number of visits to the "Enter" and "Browse" states.

Similarly, when the transition probability from "Login to Filling the Form" decreases by 10%, the average number of visits to the "Filling the Form" state decreases slightly. This indicates that users are less likely to engage with forms when the transition probability from login is reduced.

High Sensitivity Transitions. Some transitions exhibit higher sensitivity, meaning that small changes in the transition probabilities result in significant shifts in user behavior. These transitions might be crucial for e-government system designers to focus on when optimizing user flow. For example, "Enter to Browse" and "Browse to Search" transitions have substantial effects on the visits to the relevant states, indicating that users frequently engage with these parts of the e-government system.

Low Sensitivity Transitions. On the other hand, transitions such as "Filling the Form" and "Exit" have relatively low sensitivity. This suggests that users are less likely to be influenced by small changes in these transitions, and their behavior remains relatively stable despite adjustments in probabilities. These states may require less attention in terms of capacity planning and optimization, compared to highly sensitive transitions.

System Behavior & Resource Allocation. By identifying the highly sensitive transitions, organizations can allocate resources and design the user interface accordingly. For example, if "Browse" to "Search" has high sensitivity, optimizing the search functionality and ensuring that it works smoothly for users could improve the overall user experience.

The information about which transitions are more sensitive can also guide decisions about where to focus improvements or provide additional support to users (e.g., providing better search options or more straightforward navigation paths).

Further studies could explore additional scenarios, such as varying multiple transition probabilities simultaneously or conducting a deeper analysis of user

behavior patterns at different times of day or during peak usage periods of e-government system. Moreover, integrating real user data could further enhance the accuracy of the sensitivity analysis and lead to more clear optimization strategies.

Conclusion

Sensitivity analysis offers a powerful tool for understanding user interactions within a e-government system and provides actionable insights for enhancing e-government system design, improving the user experience, and optimizing performance. Organizations can use these insights to make strategic adjustments to their e-government system's architecture, design, and features. For example, streamlining the "Filling the Form" process or improving the "Search" functionality can help cater to users' needs and improve the overall e-government system efficiency. By focusing on the most sensitive transitions, e-government system designers can make informed decisions that have a direct and positive impact on user engagement and overall e-government system efficiency.

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